

MRT (CT) DATA IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF COMPLICATIONS OF LUMBAR RADICULOPATHY

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TEZIS

Introduction: One of the most common manifestations of osteochondrosis of the lumbar spine is a herniated intervertebral disc. Lumbar radiculopathy can be aggravated by a number of complications that can lead to surgery. To study the complications that may develop lumbar radiculopathy, which will ensure improved patient care, both conservative and repeated surgical.

The purpose of the study: to analyze the results of tomography (MRI and CT) in complications of lumbar radiculopathy.

Materials and methods

The analysis of MRI and CT data was carried out in 21 patients with a clinical picture

with complications due to decompression of the lumbar spinal roots who were treated in the neurological department at the clinic of the Bukhara State Medical Institute named after Abu Ali ibn Sina during 2023-2024. In this group, 21 tomographic examinations were performed for diagnosis in the period of complications, of which 12 (57.1%) MRI and 9 (42.9%) CT scans of the lumbar spine.

Results: In the study group, some patients were diagnosed with a combination of several types of pathology. At the same time, the following pathology was visualized: a true recurrence of an IVD hernia (9 people – 42.8%); the appearance of an IVD hernia on the other side (3 people – 14.2%); the formation of an IVD hernia at a new level (7 people – 33.3%); edema of the disc tissue with protrusion into the canal (2 people – 9.7%); The data obtained indicate the presence of a large number of variants of pathological changes in the spinal canal, which causes complaints and changes in orthopedic and neurological status in the early and late recovery period.

Conclusions: Most often, tomography in the early or late recovery period visualized a true recurrence of a herniated IVD (42.8%) and the formation of a herniated disc at a new level (33.3%). Inflammatory complications (discitis) were rare and amounted to 4.9%.

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